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ZAANGAŻOWANIE CYWILNE I UCZESTNICTWO JAKO WAŻNE INSTRUMENTY PRACY Z MŁODZIEŻĄ

Viktorii Karpuk

*Aspirant Wydziału Pracy Socjalnej i pedagogika szkolnictwa wyższego
Wschodnioeuropejski Uniwersytet Narodowy im. Lesi Ukrainki (Łuck, Ukraina)
e-mail: vika.karpuk21@gmail.com
ORCID ID 0000-0002-9087-5980*

Streszczenie. Ważnym czynnikiem pomyślnego rozwoju społeczeństwa obywatelskiego i procesów społeczno-kulturowych jest zaangażowanie młodych ludzi w ważne społecznie decyzje. To młodzi ludzie muszą zająć się kwestiami, które bezpośrednio ich dotyczą, a inni uczestnicy powinni ich wspierać, a nie wskazywać, co należy zrobić. W artykule wskazano, że zaangażowanie obywatelskie i uczestnictwo to zaangażowanie młodych ludzi w działalność wolontariacką i społeczną, zwiększenie udziału młodzieży w procesach decyzyjnych, tworzenie organów doradczych, tworzenie mechanizmów wsparcia dla wdrażania edukacji obywatelskiej itp. Istnieje wiele form uczestnictwa młodzieży w publicznych procesach decyzyjnych: udział w wyborach; rady gmin; przesłuchania publiczne; lokalne inicjatywy; udział w działaniach organizacji społeczeństwa obywatelskiego; młodzieżowe projekty społeczne; kluby zainteresowań; tworzenie sieci peer-to-peer i tym podobnych.

Słowa kluczowe. młodzież; uczestnictwo młodzieży; zaangażowanie obywatelskie; społeczeństwo obywatelskie; demokracja.

CIVIL INVOLVEMENT AND PARTICIPATION AS AN IMPORTANT INSTRUMENT IN WORKING WITH YOUTH

Viktorii Karpuk

*Ph.D. student Department of Social Work and Pedagogy of Higher School
Lesya Ukrainka East-European National University (Lutsk, Ukraine)
e-mail: vika.karpuk21@gmail.com
ORCID ID 0000-0002-9087-5980*

Abstract. An important factor for successful development of civic society and socio-cultural processes is the involvement of young people in making socially important decisions. These are young people who have to resolve problems that directly affect them, and other participants should support them, but not order what to do.

The aim of the article is to investigate civil involvement and participation as an important instrument of the work with youth. On the basis of literature sources analysis the article determines that civic engagement and participation is the involvement of young people in volunteer and community activities, increase of youth participation in decision making processes, creation of advisory board, formation of enabling mechanisms for the implementation of civic education etc. There are many forms of youth participation in public decision-making processes: participation in elections; social councils; public hearings; local initiatives; participation in the activities of civil

society organizations; youth social projects; interest clubs; peer-to-peer networking etc. Youth participation can also be viewed as a form of youth-adult partnership. The advantage of partnership between young people and adults is that it benefits from the young people's skills and talents, as well as from the experience and knowledge of adults.

The article determines that civic engagement among young people can be developed with the introduction of civic education. Civic education helps young people to be well-informed active citizens involved in policy-making and democratic governance. In order to work with young people effectively it has been suggested to improve their participation in democratic structures and processes, expressing of opinions with the help of advisory boards formed at the organs of local self-government from the youth representatives for advising, development and realization of youth politics at local level. Therefore youth councils creation is an effective form of youth participation in addressing issues that directly affect young people.

Key words: youth; youth participation; civic engagement; civil society; democracy.

ГРОМАДЯНСЬКА ЗАЛУЧЕНІСТЬ ТА УЧАСТЬ ЯК ВАЖЛИВИЙ ІНСТРУМЕНТ У РОБОТІ З МОЛОДДЮ

Вікторія Карпук

*аспірантка кафедри соціальної роботи та педагогіки вищої школи
Східноєвропейського національного університету імені Лесі Українки
(Луцьк, Україна)*

e-mail: vika.karpuk21@gmail.com

ORCID ID 0000-0002-9087-5980

Анотація. Важливим чинником для успішного розвитку громадянського суспільства та соціокультурних процесів є залучення молодих людей до прийняття суспільно важливих рішень. Саме молоді люди повинні вирішувати проблеми, що безпосередньо їх торкаються, а інші учасники повинні підтримувати їх, а не вказувати, що необхідно робити.

Мета статті – дослідити громадянську залученість та участь як важливий інструмент у роботі з молоддю. На основі аналізу літературних джерел у статті визначено, що громадянська залученість та участь являє собою залучення молоді до волонтерської та громадської діяльності, підвищення участі молоді у процесах прийняття рішень, створення консультативно-дорадчих органів, питання створення механізмів підтримки щодо впровадження громадянської освіти тощо. Існує безліч форм участі молоді в процесах вирішення суспільних питань: участь у виборах; громадські ради; громадські слухання; місцеві ініціативи; участь у діяльності організацій громадянського суспільства; молодіжні соціальні проєкти; клуби за інтересами; створення мереж «рівний-рівному» тощо.

У статті визначено, що громадянська залученість серед молоді може формуватись шляхом впровадження громадянської освіти. Громадянська освіта допомагає молоді бути добре проінформованими, активними громадянами, залученими у процеси вироблення політики та демократичного управління. Для ефективної роботи з молоддю запропоновано покращити їхню участь в

демократичних структурах і процесах, висловленні своїх думок шляхом створення консультативно-дорадчих органів, які утворюються при органах місцевого самоврядування із представників молоді для консультування, розробки та реалізації молодіжної політики на місцях. Тому саме створення молодіжних рад є дієвою формою участі молоді в процесі вирішення питань, які безпосередньо стосуються молодих людей.

Ключові слова: молодь; участь молоді; громадянська залученість; громадянське суспільство; демократія.

Introduction. The necessity for theoretical comprehension of role and importance of youth resource has been timely as young people are directly connected to new steps towards democratic future of the country. Thus it is vital for the successful development of civil society and socio-cultural processes. In this context, local government is in charge of proper determining of youth work development directions, taking into account young people's interests. Additionally, democracy requires active participation of young citizens in society, in decision creation processes, and the conditions for such participation as well. Therefore the important success factor is young people engagement in socially important decision making.

The concept of «youth participation» is defined in the introductory part of the Revised Charter on the participation of young people in local and regional life: «Participation in the democratic life of any society is more than simple voting, balloting in the elections, however all of them are important components. Participation and active citizenship mean rights, means, space, opportunities and, if necessary, support in decision making. Active citizenship also means participation in various activities and processes aimed at building better society». The notion of participation defined by the Charter indicates a change in approach to the youth and their involvement in public life. Young people are seen as active participants of society or organizations, partners with great potential, full of strength and talents. These are young people who have to decide problems that directly affect them, and other participants should support them, but not order what to do.

Outline of the main research material. It is worth noting that youth participation and civic education have been getting considerable attention all over the world recently. We have identified that civic engagement and participation is the involvement of young people in volunteer and community activities, increase of youth participation in decision making processes, creation of advisory board, formation of enabling mechanisms for the implementation of civic education etc.

The practice of youth participation has proven to be an effective form of work with youth. After all, participation is an indicator of young people's active civic position and a kind of indicator of personal development. It is impossible to learn anything, develop or acquire skills if you are passively observing. Only in the process of participation young people gain experience, practical skills, self-confidence, knowledge required. Communication skills, the ability to navigate the information space, plan their actions, predict results and take responsibility for decision-making are developed in the process of cooperation and dialogue between adults / leaders and youth (*Zhukova 2010, 15-16*).

Sometimes the situation in the youth environment and in the competence sphere of state youth policy is characterized by acute problems. In particular, young people do

not show any initiative and do not want to participate in decision making. Presumably, they do not want to take responsibility, they are afraid of difficulties or they will not be able to take any action in a good and timely manner. It is quite a natural position and it should be respected as well. In our opinion, youth participation in decision-making is necessary and important.

It is needed to take into account the following basic principles while creating the proper conditions for youth participation:

➤ young people's participation in public life enables them to make their own choices;

➤ politics generally takes better account of young people's needs owing to youth participation;

➤ if youth problems are taken seriously by the community, then young people are also aware of their share of responsibility in community life;

➤ young people have to decide what kind of community participation they can take, and they should not obey adult instructions (*Have your say 2015, 39-41*).

Youth workers are convinced that it is necessary to increase youth involvement in community activities. It means not only attending informal events or training programs, but also an active role in the preparation, planning, realization and evaluation of community activities. Young people who actively volunteer at youth centers and clubs need to develop leadership skills and instruct the youth in civic competences so that they can eventually implement their own skills (*Borenko, Donetsk 2018, 8*).

Roger Hart (an author of «The Ladder of Participation») believes that participation is a fundamental right of a citizen, because it gives him/her an opportunity to learn what it means to be a citizen. Council of Europe understands the participation of the youth as «the right of young people to be involved in public life, take responsibilities and duties in daily life at the local level and influence their lives in democratic ways». Youth participation can also be viewed as a form of youth-adult partnership. Partnership means working together. This means that goals, ambitions, responsibilities, decisions are discussed and approved by both sides. Young people and adults know what is expected from them, what they expect from others, how to do it and what kind of support they receive. The advantage of partnerships between young people and adults is that it benefits from the young people's skills and talents, as well as from the experience and knowledge of adults.

A certain set of tools should be given to young people in order to achieve real youth participation. This entails advancing education in the sphere of young people's participation, keeping them informed, providing them with communication tools, supporting youth projects. Participation arises with dedication, recognizes the role of young people in political parties, public associations, creates joint efforts to promote the formation of the youth associations with the participation of young people themselves (*Pilgun, Kolobov, Yeleneva 2014, 14*).

It should be noted that civic engagement among young people can be developed by the introduction of civic education. Civic education helps young people to be well-informed, active citizens involved in policy-making and democratic governance. Civic education is defined as a national priority at the state level in accordance with the National Strategy for Promoting Civil Society Development for 2016 – 2020, and the

State Target Social Program «Youth of Ukraine» for 2016 – 2020. The Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine has also included civic education in the secondary school curriculum (*Volyn Regional State*).

For example, the Ministry of Youth and Sports of Ukraine in cooperation with the United Nations Development Program, the State Institute for Family and Youth Policy continue to implement the training program «Workers with Youth». A specialized training course «Civic Education for Workers with Youth» has been implemented within the program.

After having passed such a training program, the youth worker can help young people to be active citizens, understand human rights and their own identity, be interested in social processes, critically evaluate them, and be the driving force of these processes as well.

The aim of the course is to increase the capacity of youth workers to support and actively engage youth in decision-making processes at local and regional level. The training will provide youth workers with the competencies that are needed to implement civic education programs for youth. These programs are aimed at achieving positive change in the community. And due to the training youth workers will also acquire practical tools how to implement civic education initiatives for youth in the community.

Youth participation in processes of community well-being formation has been still a new experience for Ukraine. «Nothing for us is without us». This principle of youth policy development and community life has been slowly starting to penetrate in all the spheres of public life. Participation is fundamental human right. Young people have to decide how exactly they can participate in civic life. It is clear that they aspire to live in better, more democratic society and are prepared for some action for this purpose, but they often do not know how to act (*Revised European Charter on Youth Participation in Local and Regional Life 2015*).

Participation of young people in decision-making processes is carried out in the forms defined by the legislation, normative legal acts of local authorities and according to the established practice that has developed within the competence of a specific territorial community.

There are various forms of youth participation in public decision-making. Young people can participate in many areas, from voluntary work to active participation in organizations, from participation in non-formal education to campaigning. Among the common forms of youth participation such ones can be distinguished as participation in elections (to vote and be elected), community councils, public hearings, local initiatives, participation in the activities of civil society organizations, youth social projects, interest clubs, peer networking (involving young people in the education process of their peers on the principle of equality), organizations of forums in order to discuss current issues, petition signing, creation of thematic groups in social networks, participation in different types of non-formal learning, etc (*Pilgun, Kolobov, Yeleneva 2014, 23*).

Institutional forms of youth participation on local and regional levels include youth councils, youth parliaments or youth forums, which, for example, should be permanent structures composed of elected or appointed representatives and should give young people direct responsibility for projects and policy influence etc.

Youth councils creation is an effective form of youth participation in addressing issues that directly affect young people. On January 14, 2019 the policy directive on youth advisory boards (youth councils) was approved by the government.

The Youth Council is a youth voice tool that enables young people to be heard. This is the advisory board that is formed at the local self-government bodies and it consists of youth representatives who consult, develop and implement youth policies at the local level. There have already been over 80 youth advisory boards in Ukraine. All of them have various directives, different structure and potential. Some councils are created by specific persons (mayors, heads of regional state administrations), and other ones at the executive bodies of city councils (youth management, departments of family, youth and sports). Such diversity often leads to the fact that councils do not cooperate with each other and they are different bodies according to their directives (*Public Space 2019*).

For instance, the City Council has decided to create the Youth Council at the Lutsk City Council. The aim of it is to create a permanent collegial advisory board at the Lutsk City Council in order to consult with the public regarding the formation and implementation of youth state policy and address city life issues.

Such tasks of the Youth Council can be distinguished as the development of recommendations, proposals on the implementation of youth policy to the executive bodies of the city council, involvement of youth in participation in all the spheres of city development, promotion of a healthy and safe lifestyle, dissemination of volunteer movement among young people which is aimed at improving young citizens' social situation and lives, identification and justification of youth policy top directions, monitoring the formal and informal public youth organizations activities, the student government bodies of the city (*Lutsk City Council 2019*).

Another example of work with youth in Volyn region is the Youth Council formed at the Volyn Regional State Administration which is an advisory board at the regional level. Such a body facilitates youth participation in the process of devising, issuing acts on implementation of state policy in the youth sphere at the regional level, youth involvement in addressing the socio-economic, political and cultural life of the region, and proposal development for identifying and justifying of top directions of how to implement state policy in the youth sphere and how to conduct work at the regional level. The Youth Council also involves socially active youth in the implementation of state policy in the youth sphere at the regional level (*Volyn Regional State Administration 2019*).

It is worth noting that these youth councils are similar in structure, tasks and areas of activity, but, in one instance, these activities take place within the city, and, in another one, within the region. Local and regional authorities are closest to the youth. And their role is of paramount importance in promoting youth participation. Moreover, local and regional authorities can ensure that young people have the opportunity to get acquainted with the principles of democracy and citizenship, and they also have the possibility to practice these principles.

Conclusion. Young people can make significant contribution to the lives of society and community. It is the youth who is the best expert in solving youth problems. Young people can advance non-standard ideas, make suggestions and implement them for the benefit of civil society. They have to participate in democratic structures and processes, express their opinions and make decisions that affect them and their lives. If young people's aim is to build more democratic society, their participation is indispensable.

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